

THE PRACTICE OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT IN CHILDREN BASED ON PSYCHOLINGUISTIC FUNCTIONS.

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As part of sociolinguistics, linguists invariably recognize the need to study the social functions of languages such as ontolinguistics, persolinguistics, psycholinguistics, and their place in human society. For example, in 1958, the English psychologist B. Bernstein began to analyze the language of London youth. It will form two groups of young people aged 15-18 for the experiment. The first group includes young people who do all kinds of physical work and do not have secondary education. The second group consisted of children of the same age, but studying in prestigious private schools in London, with a strong desire to learn. B. Bernstein calls the first group the "low class" and includes the rural population of England, people engaged in agriculture. The second group is called "middle class", and it is emphasized that representatives of the upper, middle and intermediate classes belong to it. As a result of the experiments, B. Bernstein concludes that the language level and level of language acquisition of "low-class" children is limited and low compared to high-class children. Children of the first group conduct their speech as a "limited code". Their speech is syntactically composed of the same simple and short sentences, sentences are incomplete, prepositions, conjunctions, and adverbs are rarely used, answers and references are clear and concise. The second group has a "widespread code" and their speech is formed on the basis of choice; syntactic units are characterized by their completeness and complexity, efficient use of various tools of the language, wide use of prepositions, conjunctions, code lexicon and semantics. The speech of the first group can be foreseen and imagined; and the possibility of understanding the speech of the second group in advance is extremely small. Therefore, B. Bernstein says that there is a similarity between the social stratification in society and the social differentiation of language, that 29% of the population of England belong to the lower class, thus there is a shortage of language in the lower class, compensation to bring it to a high level of "common code" (compensation of the deficiency) states the necessity. This theory was used for pedagogical purposes in Germany in the 60s of the 20th century. Based on the above, it is possible to conclude that a person's speech is first of all closely related to the environment in which he lives - that is, space and time.

Ontolinguistics is the first stage of formation of individual speech, which is mainly formed in the family. As it is an undeniable fact that the role of the family in the formation of a person as a person is an undeniable fact, ontolinguistics is important as the first stage of the formation of human speech. For example, our great grandfather Hazrat Navoi used 26,035 new words, and in this regard, he is more than the famous representatives of the world, such as Pushkin (21,193), Shakespeare (more than 20,000), Cervantes (more than 18,000), Jami (17,600), A. Tokai (14,000). used many new words from wordsmiths. The first reason why the poet achieved such a result is that he was born in the family of Ghiyasiddin, that is, in the family of a palace official, and there were frequent meetings in his family, and young Alisher also participated in them. When we get acquainted with the biography of the poet, we can see that he read and even memorized F. Attar's work "Mantiq-ut-tyr" when he was 4-5 years old, and at the end of his life he wrote "Lison-ut-tyr" as a response to it. Therefore, in the formation and development of a person's speech, the environment in which he lives and the created conditions are of great importance. After all, the place and role of ontolinguistics in the formation of human speech, like any building rising from the foundation, cannot be equated with anything.

The great thinker, encyclopedist Abu Ali Ibn Sina paid special attention to the issues of morality and manners, education and training. He emphasizes the importance of memorizing the Qur'an, teaching the structure of poetry to children under 14 years of age, conducting meaningful moral conversations with them, implementing physical education, and making them masters of a profession. The role of fiction in educating the young generation as a physically, mentally and spiritually mature, socially active person is incomparably great. Children's monologue speech is formed in the process of introduction to these fictions, i.e. fairy tales, stories, and narratives. The main goal of the literary classes is to instill in the hearts of children a desire for literary books, as well as to increase their reading literacy and reading culture.

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